

STRONG ARTISTIC IMAGES IN RUSSIAN AND UZBEK LITERATURE

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Abstract. *The article analyzes the history of the creation of a strong image in Russian and Uzbek literature, the role of women in the history of the two peoples, contributing to the creation of a female image in Russian and Uzbek literature.*

Keywords: *position of a woman, freedom of choice, fate, upbringing, duties, purpose.*

Introduction. Throughout the long and difficult history of Russia, radical changes have occurred more than once in society. How many wars, revolutions and social upheavals took place in the country. Over time, the usual way of life was redrawn, new norms of behavior were introduced, and fashion changed. And if for the male part of the population many changes were so painful, then for women it was a big test - from the struggle for the right to receive an education, to defend their rights and ending with the right to remain themselves.

The idea of the position of women in society is in many ways reminiscent of today. In the customs and culture of the ancient Slavs, the roles of both sexes were always taken into account, and no gender bias was observed. Women had freedom of choice in concluding marriage relations, enjoyed respect and honor in the tribe. And in the Muslim society (Uzbek family) the role of women was very weak. The woman was deprived of many rights. She was basically the keeper of the hearth. They always went covered in a veil, did not have the right to study in public schools, and were not supposed to be conspicuous even on the street. Marriages were mostly given by parents, without taking into account the consent of their daughters. And the rich and khans had harems and concubines. In the Muslim religion, a woman, a daughter, must respect the decision of her parents, as they will not wish them harm. In the family, the word of the man is always the law, the value of the family and loyalty to the husband was put above the personal interests and desires of the woman, and the principle "but I am given to another and will be faithful to him forever" was to become, on occasion, a life credo for girls. The role of a mother and a reliable support for her husband is her main purpose.

Strong artistic images live longer than their creators, exerting a huge influence on the attitudes and behavior of readers. Images turn into symbols, forming "Bridges" into an ideal world. Heroes of works of fiction connect the past and the future, reality and fiction.

The study of the artistic heritage of outstanding authors has always attracted the attention of a wide range of researchers, linguists and literary critics. Of great interest is the study of the means and techniques used by authors of fiction to create the imagery of their works and aesthetic impact on the reader. All this is achieved due to the fact that various expressive and emotional shades are added to the purely logical content of the works.

One of the most common tropes is figurative comparison. It gives speech a special expressiveness. Of particular interest is the analysis of figurative comparisons in works of fiction, the ways in which they reveal the author's view of various objects, phenomena and heroes, that is, the identification of the special role of figurative comparison in reflecting the

artistic intention of the writer. In our study, we adhere to the definition of M.D. Kuznets and Yu.M. Skrebnev, who define figurative comparison as "the comparison of two objects that have any common feature for them, in order to more vividly and visually characterize one of them" [1, p. 145].

Since prehistoric times, women have been the object of "male art." This is what we are told by the so-called "Venus" - stone figurines of pregnant women with large breasts. Literature for a long time remained male, because, there is and what a man saw in a woman. The woman was and is still the subject of worship (from the ancient mysteries to the Christian veneration of the Virgin Mary). The Russian national character found its bright embodiment in the work of N.S. Leskov. The writer managed to reveal the depth and essence of the nature of the Russian man. And in Uzbek literature, Abdulla Kadiri's novel "Past Days" reveals the widest range of universal human themes and problems. Therefore, it is very difficult to define it unambiguously. But still it can be argued that, having laid the basis of the work a beautiful love story, the author was able to touch upon the most difficult problem of the confrontation between God and the devil, light and darkness in the fate of mankind.

In the work of N.S. Leskov, there are several types of Russian female characters: humble, virtuous, predatory, which in turn represent different facets of the manifestation of rich Russian nature. And in the novel "Bygone Days" we are faced with the multifaceted narrative, the presence of side plots, consistent and increasing intensity and a tragic denouement of events.

The ideological and compositional center of the novel is the image of Otabek, who adheres to advanced views. He openly opposes outdated methods of conducting trade and economic relations, adheres to new views on family and domestic problems. There is a conflict between Otabek and conservative forces that hinder development in the region. In many ways, Abdullah Kadiri puts his own thoughts and judgments into the mouth of his hero. In parallel, the writer traces the fate of the Uzbek woman. Inhuman and cruel practices, in particular polygamy, lead to the deadly feud between two women, Kumush and Zainab. With special love and sincerity, the writer draws the image of the beautiful Kumush, who, thanks to pure and all-consuming love for Otabek, overcomes the trials of life and the cunning of enemies. However, tragedy is inevitable. She dies, poisoned by them, and Otabek dies in battle with the enemies of her homeland.

In fiction, they often resort to the use of figurative comparisons to achieve expressiveness of speech and convey the characteristic features of the characters. When creating female images, the use of comparisons allows you to create an original description of the appearance of the heroines, their behavior, feelings, thoughts and the world around them. Comparisons in the speech of the characters can give a figurative description of various actions and deeds of people, determine the psychological and physical state of a person, his worldview, circumstances, positions and situations in which the heroine of the work found herself.

A. Kadyri, being the founder of a realistic novel of a new type in Uzbek literature, through a variety of forms and styles mastered ideological and aesthetic views. Uzbek fiction, as part of the national heritage and an enduring cultural value, reflects the rich history of the Uzbek people. "Russian women" Nekrasov. The life of these girls was filled with lush entertainment and creative fantasies. A happy childhood smoothly turned into a youth full of pleasant excitements. Girls shone at balls and occupied a high position in secular society. Court fun and music, theatrical performances and high-society techniques - these activities were the usual way of life

of young aristocrats. Smart and charming in their youth and beauty, both girls met their true love and became happy in marriage. One of the heroines of the Nekrasov poem was a very real person. Ekaterina Ivanovna, who was given the name Countess Laval at birth, is known as the wife of Sergei Trubetskoy, a participant in the Decembrist uprising. The faithful wife selflessly went into exile after her husband, finding death in 1854, in Irkutsk.

Inference. Thus, we can conclude that every woman is unique and multifaceted, so from century to century artists, writers and figures can not resist her beauty. They try to catch a fleeting glance, a slight movement, to reveal hidden character traits, spiritual, moral and intellectual qualities, purity, intelligence, a heart full of love, a desire for freedom and struggle, they want to capture it in history with the help of a story, a story or a picture, this true and beautiful image. Being half of humanity, a woman occupies a significant place in the literature of any nation. The creation of an artistic image of a woman in the literature of the peoples of the East has its roots in the depths of centuries, reflected both in folklore and in written literary monuments.

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